

A Study on Authentic Classroom Interaction Patterns

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Abstract

The present-day education sector has been so challenging for the teachers. As communication and technology rise to their heights, teachers are required to upgrade their teaching standards and teaching practices in the classroom. In this respect, teachers need to learn the latest teaching patterns and keep their efforts to create an effective classroom. At this juncture, various changes have taken place in the modern classrooms. As part of this, several patterns for classroom interaction are introduced. Interaction is highly required in classroom activities. It helps the teaching and learning procedure to run smoothly and can raise interest among the learners. Maintaining interaction with the whole class is needed for a teacher to create a learner-centric environment that raises interest among students towards the subject, and active participation during class time. This refers to the conversation between the teachers and students, as well as among the students themselves, in which active participation and learning of the socio-cultural activities is possible. Through this students develop their knowledge and focus on the learning patterns collaboratively. The present paper deals with various patterns and implementation in an interactive classroom concerning my personal experience during the course period of my Bachelor of Education.

Keywords: Interactive Classroom, Learner-centric Environment, Patterns.

Introduction

Interaction in the classroom either at the school level or college level refers to the conversation between the teachers and students, as well as among the students themselves. Active participation and learning from one another become vital always. In our regular personal and social activities several situations take place to interact among various parties. This has been trained and practised in the classrooms.

Two ways to refer to classroom interaction

- (i) **Educational Talk or Exploratory Talk and**
- (ii) **Presentational Talk**

The purpose of educational talk or exploratory talk is to allow students to engage in broken or full of dead-end conversations that will allow them to try new ideas to hear how they sound and to see what others make to arrange their ideas into different discourse patterns. Educational talk or exploratory talk is frequently intentionally designed by teachers.

Presentational talk is a one-way lecture delivered by teachers in the classrooms, which makes minimal effort to inspire and include students in a communicative discussion. When students connect, they create a sort of symmetric dialogic context where everyone may take part, be treated with respect, and make decisions together. Thus, by taking part in interactions, students can develop their linguistic resources and increase their confidence in speaking to others. To analyze the process of interaction with each student and with the

whole class, a few activities are being conducted for the students of 9th standard, in a Govt. High School, at Rajampet, Annamayya District, Andhra Pradesh.

Review of Literature

Edwards, A. D., & Westgate, D. P. (1994) in the book "Investigating Classroom Talk" provide a comprehensive analysis of the possible classroom interactions by focusing on the linguistic and social dynamics that influence educational outcomes among the learners. The authors emphasize the significance of conversation and question the domination of teacher-led conversations in classrooms. They advocate for student-centred interaction to foster deeper understanding and critical thinking in the classroom learning process.

Hall, J. K., & Walsh, M. (2002) in the article "Teacher-student interaction and language learning" explored the relationship between teacher-student interaction and the language learning process. The research findings enquire on how the different interaction patterns such as initiation-response-feedback (IRF) affect the language acquisition level of the learners. The study points to the need to improve the interaction patterns to enhance the language learning process in classroom settings.

Nuthall, G. (2007) in the book "The Hidden Lives of Learners" studied the existing complexities of classroom interactions and their impact on the student learning process in classrooms. Through observational studies, the author argues for more personalized and receptive interaction patterns in the learning process. Only interaction-based methods can cater the easy mode to the students with active engagement.

Mercer, N., & Hodgkinson, S. (2008) in the book "Exploring Talk in School: Inspired by the Work of Douglas Barnes" examined the role of conversational talk in educational settings. It mainly discusses how different interaction patterns such as exploratory talk enhance the learning process among the learners by encouraging the students to articulate their thoughts, test each other and construct knowledge collaboratively in an active classroom environment.

Kumpulainen, K., Hmelo Silver, C. E., & César, M. (2009) in the report entitled "Investigating Classroom Interaction: Methodologies in Action" explores the various methodologies for studying classroom interactions. They highlighted the importance of authentic communication in promoting collaborative learning among the teacher and learner. The book also includes many case studies and theoretical perspectives that clearly demonstrate how interaction patterns in the classroom environment impact student engagement and learning.

Markee, N. (2015) in the edited handbook entitled "The Handbook of Classroom Discourse and Interaction" covers a wide range of topics related to classroom discourse and interaction among teachers and learners. It also provides theoretical frameworks, methodological approaches and practical applications to analyze and improve interaction methods in classroom educational settings. They highlighted the requirement for extra interactive methods and conversational methods teaching practices.

Vermunt, J.D., Donche, V. A. (2017) in the paper entitled "Learning Patterns Perspective on Student Learning in Higher Education: State of the Art and Moving Forward" aimed to portray the state of research and theory development for the student learning patterns in higher education and the possible methods that support them.

Agustin, Helin & Noviyenty, Leffi & Utami, and Henny (2019) in their article entitled "An Analysis of Classroom Activities Pursuant to Effective Techniques Teaching English in Integrated Vocational Schools" found the techniques that the teachers used to stimulate the classroom activities that suit the elements of effective teaching for the students. They also

pointed out that the chief elements of effective teaching are the use of positive support, feedback, supportive learning activities, classroom atmosphere, questioning-instruction method and indirect teaching to ensure classroom learning activities.

Glaser, G., Kupetz, M., & You, H.-J. (2019) in the article entitled "Embracing social interaction in the L2 classroom: Perspectives for language teacher education" discussed the significance of Social Interaction in Second Language (L2) Classrooms. The paper emphasizes the importance of conducting language teacher education programs to incorporate training and promote authentic classroom interactions in classroom settings.

Thanh Vu Thi and Duyen Dao Thuy (2021) in the study "A Study on Interaction Patterns in Language Learning Online Classes – Adaptation and Efficiency" found that the outcomes differed from class to class for the interaction forms among the teacher group and the student-student groups. The teachers found that their teaching experience with the students and the student's English language competence emphasized the forms of interaction in classrooms.

Such references offer a methodical examination of authentic classroom interaction patterns and provide valuable insights for educators, researchers and learners to enhance educational practices in classrooms. Based on these findings, the study has been planned to estimate the authentic classroom interaction patterns for students of 9th standard, in the Government High School, Rajampet, Annamayya District, Andhra Pradesh.

Observations on the process of planning interaction

Based on the observation from the teachers, they used various techniques in the teaching and learning process. They used individual interaction techniques and conducted class games, whole class interaction, and some stage activities also. As a teacher, I felt interested and found different ways of interacting with the students in the classroom. According to the theory of Anthony, "Technique is the level at which classroom procedures are described. It is the implementation that which takes place in a classroom. It is the particular trick strategy or contrivance used to accomplish an immediate objective." The technique must be consistent with a method, and therefore in harmony with an approach as well. Teaching technique is a step or activity that the teachers use in teaching English. Another definition is that 'Technique is a way of achieving one purpose skillfully a knack' (Anthony, 2004). There are several kinds of techniques in teaching as follows (Keachie, 2006). Talking purposefully or purposelessly is very common among the students in class. Incorporating different types of interactions, achieving the lesson objectives through such interactions, ensuring that students participate in meaningful interactions, and ensuring that all students engage in conversations and learn from the teachers as well as from one another were some of the challenges that came with planning lessons with meaningful interactions.

Challenges of interactive classroom

- Naturally, controlling conversations is more difficult because of the students' disparate levels of language proficiency and the topics that generate dialogues among them and match their levels of proficiency.
- Students in the class come from a variety of cultural and linguistic backgrounds, and, commonly, each student may come with their own special set of knowledge.
- Differentiating language ability may seem simple to some or unnoticeable to others, but doing so in the classroom will have a significant impact on how students view themselves and others, as well as how they perceive the value of their cultural and linguistic background in advancing their academics.

Ways to overcome the challenges

- Teachers’ continuous monitoring and evaluation: Continuous monitoring helps the students rectify their mistakes and may also help them to Peer evaluation
- Selecting the appropriate group size
- Assigning group roles and group configurations
- Monitoring the student's teaching stage
- Evaluating at the post-teaching stage

Stages of Interactions in the Classroom

i. Interaction of the students with the teacher (whole-class interaction): As part of the whole-class interaction, the teacher became an instructor and frequently asked the students to give their opinions on a particular question about a newly introduced or previously covered subject. To ensure that all students were represented in the interaction process, students were chosen at random for the responses based on their aptitude, seating arrangement, gender, and ethnic groups.

ii. Pair Interaction (Interaction with their peers sitting together or next to them): This engagement frequently occurred before instruction, for example, to activate their conceptual framework for a subject. Students were typically required to collaborate with their partners on a topic that the teacher had provided and present it to the class as part of the assignment of group roles.

iii. Group Interaction (Groups of 4-5 students in each) During the while-teaching phase, this type of interaction frequently occurred. After reading a text, for instance, during a reading class, students could choose a concept to debate. Their conversation may centre on deepening the ideas’ application in real life, identifying a problem and its solution, or posing an original question.

Interaction Patterns for Classroom

The table.1. explains the types of interaction patterns, types of activities, the benefits of activities, the challenges for interaction, and when those activities are suitable to conduct in the classroom.

Table 1. Type of Interaction Pattern

Type of Interaction Pattern	Type of Activity	Benefits	Challenges	Suitability
Group Work	Group Discussion/ Students Debate on any social issue/ Group Guessing & Responding/ Choral Responses Vocabulary Building Games/ Memory Testing Games/ Information	Group work provides more practice opportunities, an increased variety of activities is possible, increased student creativity and the zone of Proximal Development increases.	As with pair work, the groups must be carefully selected to ensure students can work productively; not all students can work to their full potential in this situation; and assessment of student progress can be challenging.	Small groups (5 to 6 members in each group) Giving and getting tasks.

	Transfer			
Individual Work	Textbook pre-reading during the class/ Presenting a topic/ Narrating a story/ Summarizing the topic/ Asking Close-ended questions Describing any person/ object/ situation/ Reading any news item/ Pick and Speak/ Just A Minute (JAM)	Students work at their own pace, feel confident, and they can use their preferred learning styles and strategies	Students cannot get the benefit of learning from and working with their peers unless they are involved or self-motivated	Individual student participation . Giving and getting activities
Pair Work	Situational Dialogues or conversations/ Introducing others/ Asking and exchanging questions/	Students have the chance to work with and learn from their peers; struggling students can learn from more capable peers; it is especially useful for students who prefer interpersonal learning settings.	If students are not matched up well (i.e. low students together, high students together, a higher student with a low student but they do not work together, etc.) pair work won't be useful; the ability of the students to work in this way needs to be taken into consideration.	Two students participate in each activity. Giving and getting tasks.

Findings

After observing and practising the above-mentioned patterns of interactive classrooms, it is identified that these patterns and techniques are more suitable for a language classroom and less useful for other subject teachers. However, by applying other related rubrics for each subject, these interactive teaching patterns will be helpful. I observed a positive impact by using these techniques in the classroom, and that had shown a high impact on improving the skills of psycho-motor learning of students. Students have shown much interest in continuous participation. It is also very important to add listening-related activities equal to the reading, speaking, and writing skills. Along with the use of modern teaching

tools like ICT, and online learning sources, it is required to train the teachers regarding the use of various interactive teaching patterns for better understanding of the concepts and to get rid of the fear of studies among the students. This may be challenging in the initial level of teaching but this improves the participation of students in the classroom. They lose their fear of studies and also they come out of the monotonous learning environment.

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